

At: Society for the Social History of Medicine Biennial Conference 'Resistance', 16-19.07.2024, University of Strathclyde, Glasgow.

Title: 19th century Porto's Bubonic plague outbreak and the socio-cultural resistance to the public health measures

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Abstract: The conceptual systems of human health and disease are historically and culturally specific as much as the concepts of health and sickness involve culture-related constructs like normal and deviant, clean and dirty, purity and danger, but as also the approaches to healthcare and to biocultural adaptation are historically and culturally defined. Michel Foucault's work has left very clear the relation between knowledge and power, particularly in what he called biopower. Having the majority of us experienced recently the COVID-19 pandemic that brought a novel series of daily life restrictions to whom different people reacted in favour or against, this presentation brings the case of the Portuguese city of Porto that in 1899 registered an outbreak of bubonic plague. Porto of the later 1800s was a city with mostly and pre-modern urbanism heavily

populated by recent industrialization that produced strong inward migrations. Ricardo Jorge, a Porto born physician and the Head of the city's Municipal Services of Health and Hygiene correctly identified the pathogen and led the Public Health measures aimed at controlling the epidemic. The panoply of Public Health measures advised by Ricardo Jorge were effective in controlling the epidemic, but such measures had considerable political, social, and economic repercussions with the city inhabitants rebelling strongly against them. The presentation will lay out such ripples that resulted in Ricardo Jorge leaving Porto, in spite of the success of his public health measures in controlling the epidemic.

Keywords: Biopower; Public Health; Bubonic Plague; Social Resistance; History of Medicine.